

Place Of The Republic Of Kazakhstan In The System Of International Cultural Relations

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Abstract

The article considers the role of cultural relations in the harmonization of international relations. In order to create a favorable image of the country and promote national interests, cultural ties are important. In turn, cultural ties can reveal the active foundations of foreign policy as an effective tool for coordinating international relations. Therefore, it is emphasized that the need to activate cultural ties is of great importance in the national foreign policy. From the point of view of national interests, cultural ties are of national importance.

Introduction

The course of development of world civilization has also shown that the importance of national cultures is becoming increasingly important today and that each culture, in addition to adopting the types of world development that it may need, makes a significant contribution to the process of creating a universal human culture. A distinctive feature of the current era is that national cultures are cleared of closures and their relations with each other become qualitatively new.

As the Kazakh people became a nation, and the country grew, it was impossible to create a single powerful state and decide its own fate. Now he has taken a worthy place among the Member States of the United Nations and has moved on to modern, civilized relations with others.

It is known that the period of Independence was not easy for Kazakhs. There were many days and nights when the future of our state was at stake. There were facilitators both among our own and externally, who contributed to the flare-up of crucifixes. Such critical situations can be seen on the pages of periodicals, which are the annals of that time.

The state cultural policy included not only the study of the rich heritage of the Kazakh people, but also the revival of its traditions and customs – they were supposed to enrich the daily life of the country, connect our past with the present and future (Nazarbayev, 2017: 84). Once again, Kazakhstani wise people showed their cold-blooded patience, persistence and perseverance and came through all difficulties with great endurance.

The international authority of any country is determined not only by the level of economic development, military strength, political weight, but also by its cultural heritage and potential. The priorities of foreign policy are the promotion and dissemination of noble cultural values of the largest countries of the world. Because cultural ties are one of the most important resources for influencing the world of globalization today. The influential countries of the world use culture as the basis or form of achieving the goals of the foreign policy of the state. Because cultural relations are an important area of the diplomatic service.

Theoretical framework

As the main approach - the principle of studying the foreign policy of Kazakhstan - it is advisable to use a systematic approach. Moreover, taking into account the real state, formation of the foreign policy of Kazakhstan, within the framework of the system approach, it is necessary to highlight the systemic and genetic aspects.

Its general content and purpose are the concretization of traditional systemic methods. It is obvious that the peculiarities of the systemic-genetic aspect of the systems approach requires special characteristics.

Complementing the systemic method and coinciding with it in terms of the named general initial parameters, the systemic genetic aspect, in our opinion, has a number of important differences.

The systemic-genetic aspect is characterized by a greater focus on the historicism of considering the object under study. With regard to the foreign policy of Kazakhstan, this means the need to consider it in the general chain of related historical events, as well as to take into account the prospects for its future development. Historicism as a principle of concreteness in time refers to the analysis of both the past and the future. The modern independent Kazakhstan state has a unique history. It went through a difficult stage of formation, including the periods before and after the accession to Russia, the period of being a part of the USSR. And this specificity has had and is influencing the formation of the current foreign policy course of Kazakhstan. Historicism, emphasized by the systemic genetic aspect, also implies a synthesis of humanitarian and natural science methods, history and geography.

Further, the systemic-genetic aspect makes it possible to single out the factors that determine different forms of inclusion (transition) of the object under consideration (Kazakhstan's foreign policy) into the systemic state of international relations. Moreover, these forms depend both on the nature of the objective prerequisites and on the qualitative specifics of the emerging systemic education. The political image of modern Kazakhstan is still characterized by some uncertainty. Today, in many respects, the concept of Kazakhstani statehood, including its foreign policy component, is still being comprehended and initially formed. From its thoroughness, the qualitative specifics of the spiritual and ideological aspirations embedded in it, what, ultimately, will be the stages of the formation of the system of relations between Kazakhstan and the CIS countries, with its neighbors in the region, with the leading states of the world - that is, the place and role of Kazakhstan in the system of international relations.

The concept of culture as an invariant, a "frame" of public life, allows to combine in a single study both the formation of the systematic nature of Kazakhstan's foreign policy and the humanitarian "burden" of this process. Turning on the basis of a cultural-historical approach to the selected object of research, we get the opportunity to answer the question: "For what, in the name of what is the foreign policy of Kazakhstan carried out and should it be pursued?"

The significance of the cultural and historical aspect of the systematic approach directly for the study of Kazakhstan's foreign policy is due to the rather large national and cultural originality of the country and the fact that the processes of the formation of the public in Kazakhstan, the formation of the foundations of Kazakhstani statehood are going along with the national and cultural self-determination of Kazakhstan in the complex realities of the modern world.

It is important to highlight the basic values and cultural orientations of Kazakhstan, its position in the world and regional historical and cultural process - that is, the semantic core around which geopolitics should be formed and built in the international arena.

In this research, one should not forget about the close connection between the cultural-historical and systemic-genetic aspects of the general systemic principle of research.

Literature review

The first President of Kazakhstan N. Nazarbayev not only defined foreign policy goals and objectives, but also took a direct part in their implementation. The participation of the First President in international forums, the coverage of the country's foreign policy interests and positions, the holding of bilateral and multilateral negotiations, the signing of political and diplomatic documents of various degrees, etc. indicate that the issue of foreign policy was under his constant control. Therefore, books and articles written by N. Nazarbayev are important literature on the external political and cultural relations of Kazakhstan with foreign countries (Ayagan, Nurumbetova, Abzhanov, 2010: 368).

Great interest is aroused by the work of the current president of Kazakhstan, and before that diplomat K. Tokayev, "Kazakhstan's foreign policy in the context of globalization" when it comes to the study of international politics. But the author partially examines only in the context of general issues of international relations in relation to cultural ties of Kazakhstan with foreign countries. That is, he mainly studies political, economic, military-strategic and scientific-technical aspects of relations between Kazakhstan and foreign countries. However, he pays attention to cultural ties only to a lesser extent (Tokaev, 2000: 584).

The monograph of Doctor of Political Sciences Mukhamedov M.B. reveals the process of the Republic of Kazakhstan joining the world community and the history of the formation and features of political, economic, cultural and humanitarian relations of Kazakhstan with Russia and the countries of Central Asia, as well as with China, Turkey in the period 1991-1999 years (Mukhamedov, 2000: 328). However, as we can see, in these fundamental works, the author did not consider cultural ties as a special study.

Mazhidenova D.M. in her work warns: "Foreign cultural policy is an integral part of state policy in the international arena. A developed national culture, relying on a certain cultural policy, can become a reliable tool for protecting national identity and countering external cultural expansion" (Mazhidenova, 2011: 59-61).

Diplomat Arystanbekova A.Kh. in her monograph notes that "globalization of cultures is a complex

and deep process. This is an intense cultural exchange between human society, associated with the unprecedented development of modern means of communication, as well as with the constant movement of large sections of people around the world (legal and illegal). However, not always an alternative. Today, the interaction of cultures is realized through the carriers of various cultural traditions, through direct connections of many people, the interference of one culture into another. Culture is the most important symbol of identity and belonging. Culture is the most sensitive area to globalization. Therefore, despite the fact that globalization contributes to the rapprochement of people, it should not lead to the identification of cultures. On the contrary, globalization should allow people to gain access to culture, ideas and knowledge with a rich creative potential " (Arystanbekova, 2007: 238-258). Summing up, cultural cooperation plays an important role in the realization of national interests, security, the establishment of peaceful, equal relations, further development of integration relations between countries. Cultural interaction remains an important factor in relations between states, since cultural ties play an important role in the rapprochement of states. It also contributes to mutual understanding between peoples, maintaining peace, preventing conflicts and protecting human rights.

Western scholars have not written about Kazakhstan's foreign cultural ties since the Soviet era. They often consider the global challenges only in the geo-economic, geopolitical context of Kazakhstan, that is, in terms of the importance of Kazakhstan and its place there.

Several Turkish scholars have written on foreign cultural relations. In particular, Serdar Yilmaz "Kazakhstan-Turkey Economic and Cultural Relations: promises and facts"; Seyit Ali Avcu in the context of Turkey, the European Union-Kazakhstan relations "; Mehmet Saray" Language and Culture Union in the Turkish world ", etc(<https://www.academia.edu>).

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First steps in international relations

Since gaining independence, Kazakhstan has stepped up its popularization and promotion of its national models around the world, developing a culture to the best of its ability that meets the needs of the time.

The cultural policy of the country has ensures the right of all citizens to a decent life, education and access to the health care system, regardless of religion or origin. This allowed them to freely practice their religion, learn their native language and develop their national culture(Iskakova, 2000: 55).Foreigners also comment on the tolerant policy of Kazakhstan. OSCE High Commissioner on National Minorities Mr. Van der Stoep ran as follows: «The Government of Kazakhstan implements a logical policy to create the conditions necessary for the realization of the interests of all ethnic groups living in Kazakhstan and for the further coordination of inter-ethnic relations. Adherence to this policy by the majority of civil institutions and citizens, including the OSCE, provides a solid basis for the further stabilization of inter-ethnic relations in the country». President of the Swiss Confederation Pascal Kushpen made the following statement at a press conference held in Bern «Kazakhstan is an island of stability in Central Asia, where due respect is paid to the most important human rights such as the right to live in peace and the rights of national minorities»(<https://www.osce.org/odihr/38008?download=true>).

The main goal in international cultural relations of Kazakhstan was to harmonize the cultural integration of the peoples and nations of the country, to jointly promote our common heritage and our current culture on the international arena, at the world level.

The people have a saying, "Good deeds begin to move the country." During the Soviet era, it was a dream to hold large meetings not only throughout Europe even in Moscow.

Today, Kazakhstan has a high reputation within the international organizations. This is evidenced by the fact that only Kazakhstani diplomats are elected from the Central Asian states to the highest positions of such large regional associations as the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, the Eurasian Economic Community, the Organization for Economic Cooperation, TURKSOY, and the Organization for Islamic Cooperation.

It is safe to say that the special authority of Kazakhstan in the international arena proceeded from the active policy of President Nursultan Nazarbayev. Foreign partners are always trying to listen for and attentive to the opinion of the country and its leader.

Today, industry researchers are concerned about how Kazakhstani culture is gradually becoming part of a global cultural space, and what the impact of globalization is on our country. On the one hand, given the good and bad nature of Kazakhstan's mentality, there is no danger of losing our national and cultural identity due to the advent of alien values. Moreover, the global processes of cultural integration and the consequent volatile changes that could break the golden line between generations, that has already occurred in a number of developed countries.

On the other hand, Kazakhstan should not be afraid of such threats and risks. Due to the unique nature of the historical destiny, various national cultures have met and united in Kazakhstan. According to the results

of sociological research conducted by the Ministry of culture, the level of satisfaction of the population with cultural services is 66-70,3%.

Speech by Nursultan Nazarbayev at the Palace of Peace and Accord at an expanded meeting of the public Council on the implementation of the state program "Cultural heritage", "Culture is the face of the nation, its spiritual identity, its soul, its mind and its intelligence. The civilized nation, first of all, is proud of its history, its culture, its great personalities, its great and small contribution to the golden fund of world culture. And only through its own national culture can it be recognized"(<http://www.akorda.kz/>). Therefore, the promotion of our culture in the international arena is one of the most important state issues.

In today's world, cultural interaction remains an important factor in relations between states, and everyday experience shows how important its role is in the rapprochement of countries and continents. Kazakhstan's position in foreign policy today multi-vector, pragmatism and proactivity, meaning the development of friendly, equal and mutually beneficial relations with all states, interstate associations and international organizations of practical interest to Kazakhstan. Contributing to the building of a stable, just and democratic world order; equal integration into the world political, economic and humanitarian space. Ensuring favorable external conditions for the implementation of cooperation and the development of foreign policy and foreign economic priorities.

Development and implementation of cultural ties

After gaining sovereignty the state policy in the field of culture was based on the following fundamental principles in enhancing the exclusive image of Kazakhstan in the international arena:

- state support of national culture, ensuring and protecting the rights of citizens of the Republic of Kazakhstan in the field of culture and participation in cultural life;
- freedom of creative activity of citizens on their professional and non-professional (amateur) basis in accordance with their interests and abilities;
- equality of rights and opportunities of citizens in the creation, updating, storage, development, dissemination and use of cultural property;
- protection of historical and cultural heritage and ensuring continuity in their development;
- the development of cultural ties with compatriots living abroad, as one of the factors of preservation and integrity of the Kazakh national culture;
- the creation of legal guarantees for the preservation of the historical heritage of the Kazakh people and ethnic diasporas, the development and enhancement of the creative potential of society;
- freedom to join creative unions and other public associations in the manner prescribed by legislative acts of the Republic of Kazakhstan;
- development of an educational system that promotes the education of children and youth in national and world cultural values, aesthetic and patriotic education;
- assistance to cultural organizations in creating favorable conditions for their work in market conditions.

A study of government documents shows that, based on these industry principles, the state has taken control:

1. Conduct events within Kazakhstan to promote our native culture.
2. Establishing modern, world-class universities that meet international standards.
3. Support creative teams in participating in major international festivals.
4. Celebration of the anniversary of our historical figures at the UNESCO level.
5. Development of national projects that can be recognized in the international arena.
6. International-level exhibitions, presentations, forums, conferences
7. Conducting years, days of culture of Kazakhstan in the countries of the near and far abroad. (these events have a significant impact on the rapprochement and enrichment of the cultures of the Kazakhs and peoples of other countries), and oversee the publication of our literature in foreign languages.

First of all, such events in Kazakhstan are controlled by the authorities. For example, the Eurasia International Film Festival, which is regularly held in Kazakhstan, gradually became a meeting place for leading world cinematographers from Europe, Asia and America and allowed to establish creative, business and cultural ties.

Also, such events laid the foundation for the further development and prosperity of Kazakhstani cinema. During the development of domestic cinema, tremendous film projects on the history of the Kazakh people were implemented. Filmmakers from the USA, China, France, Russia and other countries took part in the production of films. In the film studio "Kazakhfilm" named after S. Aimanov, new workshops and units were established in accordance with international standards for film production, new equipment was purchased. More than 420 new masterpieces were created and new masterpieces were mastered.

A vivid example of success in film production was the film "Nomads", which was attended by leading filmmakers from Europe and America. The named movie is a joint production of Kazakhfilm film Studio with

Ram Bergman Productions. The main role was played by the famous actor Kuno Becker. Also played by famous foreign actors Jay Hernandez, Jason Scott Lee, Mark Dacascos, Archie Kao, and others. New forms and approaches to the organization of film production were mastered with the direct participation of European masters of design and opera, and famous American actors were mastered. It was an experience of joint creativity, which set new goals for the future. Such efforts have helped to further develop the culture of Kazakhstan and promote it at the international level.

Theaters from Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Tatarstan and Turkmenistan took part in the First International Central Asian Theater Festival in Almaty (Statistical Yearbook, 2007: 56).

One of the most successful events to present the culture of Kazakhstan in the international arena is the World Congress of Kazakhs (which brought together 10 million Kazakhs around the world). There was sent a message to peoples and governments of the world to preserve peace and friendship among all peoples, to prevent the war and end interethnic conflicts (Dauletov, 2002: 65).

International competitions in the class of violin, piano, soloists and classical art of the country are held under the direction of A. Musakhodjaeva, J. Aubakirova, A. Dinishev, as well as international festivals such as the art of Eurasia, the Ballet of the Gift of Tradition and the pop stage "Voice of Asia" became part of world art (F-75H; I-1; Case-4113).

In 2007 alone, more than 50 events were held at the national and international levels in the field of culture and art in the framework of the program "Development of the cultural situation for 2006-2008." These include an opera festival, a vocal performance, a puppet theater festival, as well as international competitions and festivals of various genres (F-54; I-1; Case-591). And the second forum of creative and scientific intelligence among the CIS participants was a clear factor that ensured the cultural and spiritual identification of people, the unification of nations and the reflection of the image of Kazakhstan at the world level. In addition, a republican seminar was held with the participation of 102 theater participants (F-24; I-1; Case-126).

Another way to Express Kazakhstan abroad is by writers and artists. Presentation and familiarization with the works of writers and artists in the country and abroad certainly raises the image of Kazakhstan. The state must activate the work of the Union of writers and artists of the country, support the publication of works that reveal our national existence, organize exhibitions and evenings to promote national products.

Creation of modern world-class universities that meet international standards.

For this purpose, Kazakh-Turkish lyceums have been opened since 1992 in Kokshetau, Kentau, Almaty, Kyzylorda, Aktobe, Atyrau, Shymkent, Zhambyl, Zhezkazgan, Karaganda, Ust-Kamenogorsk, Taldykorgan, Astana, Kostanay, Pavlodar and Semey. Currently, there were 25 Kazakh-Turkish lyceums and 1 primary school in Kazakhstan. These good deeds were implemented by the Kazakh-Turkish Education Fund (KATEV). These lyceums provide students with a modern education. Pupils of the lyceum receive prizes in various subject Olympiads, both in Kazakhstan and abroad.

As part of the agreement between the governments of the Republic of Kazakhstan and the Republic of Turkey, Turkestan opened the first International Kazakh-Turkish University in the world of Turkic peoples (Saudabayev, 1999: 234). The university has offices in Almaty, Shymkent, Kentau.

The Republic of Kazakhstan establishes ties with educational institutions of Russia, Turkey, the USA, Great Britain, Poland, and Germany. In 1992, 22,000 went to Russia, 914 to Turkey, 65 to Poland and 17 to the United States. By 2004, 16.4 thousand students were studying in Russia, 740 in Turkey, 500 in Poland, 500 in the United States and 250 Kazakhstani students in Egypt.

Since the 2000s, Kazakhstan's communication in the field of education has intensified between Russia and the West. Students from India, other countries of Asia, Africa came to study at universities in Kazakhstan. Children from the Kazakh diaspora (China, Mongolia, Turkey), who returned home from abroad, were educated in educational institutions of the country. At the same time, joint Kazakh-Turkish, Russian-Kazakh, Kazakh-Egyptian, Kazakh-American, Kazakh-British technical universities were opened in Kazakhstan (Kenzhebaev, 2007: 22).

As part of the student exchange program, Kazakhstani students specialize in economics, international relations, foreign philology and military research abroad. A major project in the field of education is the Bolashak state program for the training of specialists abroad.

In 2001, in Astana, together with the Soros Foundation in Kazakhstan, a round table was held on the subject "Informatization of the educational system: international experience" with the participation of specialists in the field of informatization and new technologies in the USA, Turkey and the Russian Federation. In October this year, Almaty hosted the International Forum "Informatization of Kazakhstani Education: a Step into the 21st Century", which was attended by 350 representatives from different countries and international public organizations (Djumaliev, 1995: 67).

Currently, there is a transition to a 12-year education system in accordance with the UNESCO International Standard Classification. Gender aspects have been incorporated into the standards of the 12-year

education system. It is planned to create a system of technical and vocational education. A three-level system of education was introduced (bachelor, master, doctor of philosophy).

Also today, a world-class Nazarbayev University was founded in the capital. It is one of the highest quality institutes in the world, with new institutes and institutes of independent quality. Education, innovation and research at the university is a combination of business harmony.

Formation of a university of intellectual, scientific and technical elite of Kazakhstan; transfer of knowledge, analysis and technologies provided for in accordance with the requirements of the cluster industry.

Systematic measures should be taken to ensure equal educational opportunities for all. In other words, we urgently need to develop a single online educational platform with a set of all the functions necessary for a full-fledged educational process. Timothy W. Luke confirms this statement: The work of online education creates a new political environment, creating opportunities for learning and teaching on new flexible transnational platforms that are less restricted by historically entrenched territorial areas, cultural traditions and social practices. These opportunities, in turn, create an unstable mix of negative and positive consequences, but they are neither completely positive nor completely negative (Timothy W. Luke, 2004, p. 213-226).

Support the participation of creative teams in major international festivals.

Today, the cinematic success of Kazakhstan is very significant. Films of D. Umirbayeva, E. Shynarbayeva, A. Karakulova, S. Narymbetova became laureates and prize-winners of the largest international festivals (Berlin, Cannes, Venice, Locarno, Anse, etc.). Today, Kazakhstani young filmmakers regularly participate in good film festivals in Europe. For instance, at the International Film Festival in Turin-2006, Italy, the cinematic work of director J. Zhetirova, entitled "The Body," was won. According to film critics, the image of Kazakhstani artists by cinematic means is closer to European cinema, as well as to films by such directors as Vigo, Godard, Fellini, Bergman, Visconti(F-27; I-1; Case-28).

At the same time, as a result of trips to the cities of the Russian Federation, Kyrgyzstan, Germany, South Korea, our teams gained experience and skills.

The folk ensemble "Kaynar" from the Semipalatinsk region, the state ensemble "Gulder" will go to Turkey to celebrate "Nauryz", the State Academic Ballet and Art Theater named after Abai will visit the People's Republic of China, State Chamber Orchestra of the Conservatory named after Kurmangazy at the 45th International Festival in Germany. Creative groups took part in an exhibition in San Diego, USA(Masanov, 1994: 34).

In addition, students of the Almaty Choreographic School made an official visit to Switzerland and Liechtenstein and took part in the World Ethnic Festival of the Korean National Music and Drama Theater in South Korea. As a result, people from all over the world got the opportunity to get acquainted with the culture of the Kazakh people and the artistry of artists(F-27; I-1; Case-34). All this gave the world community the cultural life of sovereign Kazakhstan in a new way.

Anniversary celebrations of our historical figures began at UNESCO. In accordance with modern principles of the sovereignty of an independent state, the reform of economic, social and cultural structures in our country is carried out from year to year, and Kazakhstan became a member of international organizations. This is the largest international organization operating on the basis of such programs as education, science and culture, "Man and the Biosphere", "Human Environment".

As a result of positive political steps to promote the culture of the people of Kazakhstan to the world, the names of Kazakhs in honor of the 150th anniversary of Abai, the 100th anniversary of M. Auezov and K. Satpayev, the 1,500th anniversary of Turkestan, Paris and London, Berlin and Tokyo are honored. Just as not before, our songs and kuys fluttered in a motive of a free and cheerful mood and this refreshed our culture, our art, our science, and also shaped our mind, worldview and personality in a new way(F-27; I-1; Case-202).

On the occasion of the 150th birthday of Abay Kunanbayev, the anniversary will be continued in Moscow and St. Petersburg, the Russian Federation, in Ankara, Izmir, Salikhli, Istanbul, in June in Paris, in Beijing, in July in Tashkent, in the capital of the People's Republic of Mongolia, in Bayan-Olga, in September in Kiev, in October in the Islamic Republic of Iran. Also in 2020, a plan of events was developed to celebrate the 175th anniversary of Abay Kunanbayev at the International, national and regional levels. In November 2020, a scientific and practical conference will be held in Paris with the participation of famous scientists and foreign literary scholars, dedicated to the anniversary of Abay Kunanbayev; A number of events dedicated to the 175th anniversary of Abay Kunanbayev are held in the UK, Turkey, Poland, Russia and China; Abay centers will be opened in the UK, France, Poland, the Czech Republic, Hungary, and Turkey.

It is a great honor to be celebrated in many countries of the world. The events not only inspired the world of our compatriots, but also demonstrated the spiritual connection between the current generation and geniuses, and in this regard the greatness of the Kazakh people.

The worldwide recognition of the work of our geniuses has strengthened the image of Kazakhstan in the world cultural space.

It is well known that the development of National Projects that can be recognized in the international

arena has not been left out. The goal of the Cultural Heritage Program was to connect our ancestors with the centuries to come. This spiritual requirement is not going to diminish in the future. One of the priorities of this document is to develop Cultural Tourism and promote the national historical and cultural heritage at the international level. It plans systematic events that highlight the development of cultural tourism based on the historic sites of the Silk Road, and their role in the history of the state as values that unite the people.

As our Silk Road has flourished for hundreds of years, Kazakhstani cities have flourished and prospered. However, for well-known historical reasons, stagnation also occurred in places other than the Silk Road, which began to weaken from the 16th century. The sad thing is that culture, along with many values, the culture of the city, the commercial culture began to disappear. When the tire turned over and the modern flame turned over, the silhouettes of the Silk Road, which stood for centuries, began to disappear. It was found in culture, cultural ties throughout the Silk Road. However, the role of Kazakhstani state "Cultural Heritage" is huge. (M. Auezov at the meeting, which was attended by representatives of non-governmental organizations from 16 countries representing the Asian Cultural Fund in China in May). The revival of the spiritual traditions of the Silk Road, the harmonization of the Silk Road culture and the values of the Silk Road, especially for Kazakhstan with its neighbor in China. Kazakhstan needs a communication model that will keep the peoples on the Silk Road. It does not have the convenience, advantages or benefits of cultural communication.

The goal of the Chinese cultural center was to promote national culture. Nevertheless, the Chinese Cultural Center at the National Library promotes good neighborly relations and good communication. Cultural relations between China and Kazakhstan are not enough. China – is a ‘giant’ neighbor. China recognizes not only Kazakhstan, but the world. In this regard, Kazakhstan must take into account another problem that equates our window to a gigantic country. These are the conditions that are characteristic of independence, sovereignty and autonomy. Therefore, we, as a country with good neighborly and interstate relations, should be aware of China's foreign policy and other aspects. Well, the Chinese cultural center in the library is a symbol of this. Significant steps are being taken through this cultural center to ensure bilateral ties that are unknown to the general public. One of the things to do is to publish the journal “Neighbor” about China in Kazakh. The magazine has also been published in China. According to the bilateral agreement, the funds will be raised by the Chinese side. Because there are also some interested people in publishing this publication in Kazakh. Moreover, Kazakhstan agree with S. Negimov’s statement, that this is a sign that the “giant” country recognizes and considers Kazakhstan, as well as its sovereignty as an independent state, which we just spoke about, in the world community”(Negimov, 2008: 7).

The study of Kazakhstani national heritage in the context of world cultural values together with foreign scientists and centers of basic research is also carried out as part of international scientific and theoretical conferences. It is planned to organize exhibitions abroad in order to popularize the national cultural heritage as a world cultural value.

In this regard, it should be recognized that the program has received international recognition in a short time. It is well known that not only the new independent states that were born on the Eurasian continent at the end of the last century, but also our large neighbors, such as China and Russia, showed special interest in the Kazakhstan model of state support for culture. Large summits, such as the Forum of Ministers of Culture of the Member States of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, indicate that the heads of delegations requested this document. At the recent summit of the leaders of the Turkic-speaking countries in Turkey, it was supposed to create such an interstate program that would allow a comprehensive study of the common cultural heritage, common identification and joint development of unique values. All this is clear and convincing evidence that the Cultural Heritage Program has had a positive impact on strengthening the country's image and maintaining a positive image among other countries.

To provide access to a modern format convenient for historical and cultural heritage, there are currently online portals: the first, a portal of cultural heritage, has fifteen chapters in all areas of the national project. In 2009, the portal service was visited by more than 200,000 people in more than 50 countries; the second is the state electronic library fund "Library of Kazakhstan". This electronic database contains over 2000 books; the third is national heritage. The portal has 22,000 museum exhibits and photographs of rarities, 6,537 museums and stock documents. In 2009, about 20,000 foreigners visited the portal(<http://cultural.kz/>). In the current information age, it is becoming clear that there are many prospects for promoting this advanced model of cultural heritage.

The archaeological heritage is one of the most important physical parts of the cultural heritage and is a cultural monument of the people.

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To provide access to the modern format convenient for the historical and cultural heritage, there are currently internet portals: the first, the Cultural Heritage portal, has fifteen chapters in all areas of the national project. In 2009, the portal service was visited by over 200,000 people in over 50 countries; the second is the Library of Kazakhstan Electronic State Library. This electronic database contains over 2,000 copies of books; the third is National Heritage. The portal has 22,000 museum exhibits and photos of rare books, 6537 museums and fund documents. In 2009, about 20,000 foreigners visited the portal(<http://cultural.kz/>). In the current information age, it is clear that there is a lot of perspective in promoting this advanced pattern of cultural heritage.

Archeological heritage is one of the most important physical part of cultural heritage and is a cultural monument of the people.

The mausoleum of Khoja Ahmed Yasawi in Turkestan is recognized by UNESCO as a unique monument of the history and culture of Kazakhstan (UNESCO)(UNESCO, 2003: 27). In addition, the archaeological complex Tamgaly was included in the UNESCO World Heritage List. Otrar is now on the list. Reconstruction and restoration of the mausoleum of Sultan Az-Zahir Beibars in Damascus in the process of increasing the international status of the State Program on Cultural Heritage and popularizing the international community as an integral part of Turkish culture, such as Al-Farabi and Sultan Az-Zahir Beibars. An agreement was reached on the construction of the Farabi mausoleum and ethno cultural center, as well as on the reconstruction of the mosque of the Sultan of Az-Zahir Beibars in Cairo(<http://cultural.kz/>).

International exhibitions, presentations, forums, conferences and publications in Kazakhstan in foreign languages are also gaining momentum. The museums of the republic are recognized worldwide for their successful work. Propagation and presentation of the history, culture and art of the Kazakh people were carried out through various exhibitions, presentations, forums, conferences, organization and holding of museum events. These events were held in the USA, China, France, Great Britain, Germany, Belgium, Japan, Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, Russia, Ukraine, Mongolia, Tajikistan and other countries(F-54; I-1; Case-208). Within the framework of the Decade of World Culture Development in the scope of UNESCO in 1992, the country hosted an international seminar on "The Role of Creative Intelligence in Implementing the Decade of the World Culture Development Decade", as well as an international festival, symposium, exhibition.

It is noteworthy that in the past cultural events reflected the ideology of "peoples' friendly laboratories", and at present international cultural programs feature numbers that reflect the folklore and folklore of the Kazakh people. It is known that such motifs can be found not only with the details (national costume, musical instruments), but also with the content of the repertoire and the skill of performing.

Since 2008, a number of our publications have been published in foreign languages. The first of these is the chronicle of the Kazakh khans, printed in France (in French). Also the series "Translation and translation of works of Kazakh literature classics into foreign languages" was launched. To date, 14 books have been published. Among them, A. Kekilbayev's work "The End of the Legend", a collection of short stories by B. Mailin "Yellow Tone", poems "The Thingy Little Bear", A. Kunanbayev's poems and words "I am a mysterious person ..." with the name "Ya - chelovek-zagadka ...", I. Yesenberlin's "Khan Kenesa", A. Tarazi's "The Fear of the Star" with the name "In the shadow of a prominence", M. Murtaza's book "The Moon and Aisha" ("Luna and Aisha"), "The White House" by S. Yelubayev to "The One-sided Yurt", the works of representatives of the outstanding Zhyrau poetry in Russian under the title "Poetry of the Zhyrau and Akyns", and B. Nurzhekeev's collection, "Guilty Love," was published in English under the title "Sinful Love.". A collection of S. Kaskabasov "Zhanazyk" is also planned to be published in English this year.

UNESCO hosted the International Scientific and Theoretical Conference on Culture and Market in Tadjikistan. Director of the Republican Scientific Center for Culture Issues M. Baltabaev took part in it.

New Aspects Of Cultural Cooperation

Days of culture of Kazakhstan are celebrated in the countries of the near and far abroad. These events have a great effect on the rapprochement and enrichment of the cultures of the Kazakh people and peoples of other countries. Another important event in promoting the national culture on the international scene is the Year of Kazakhstan in other countries. This measure not only strengthens the bilateral relations, but also helps to get acquainted with the spiritual and cultural world of the nations.

This is the expansion of international cooperation at a bilateral and multilateral level in the field of

education, science, culture, sports and youth policy; popularization of the rich historical and cultural heritage of the Kazakh people. That is, there is a systematic promotion of the goals and priorities of the foreign policy of the country, specific results and benefits for Kazakhstan in terms of increasing the foreign policy competence of society and strengthening the resilience to negative foreign policy.

On February 3, 2009, the Year of Kazakhstan in Germany was celebrated solemnly. The fact is that Europe, both politically and internationally, has a heavy political weight, and it is difficult to recognize the national art of this country, which is the center of world culture. A concert of masters of art of Kazakhstan was held in the grand concert hall of Berlin, and a photo exhibition "Kazakhstan - the heart of Eurasia" and an exhibition of the Golden Man were presented to the German public. In addition, a tour of the German Drama Theater took place on April 17-18. Exhibitions and photo exhibitions of jewelry and fine arts in Kazakhstan were organized in Munster and Berlin.

Days of Culture are celebrated in the United Arab Emirates. This country is the country where the first Persian Gulf Days of Culture took place. There, exhibitions, concerts of masters of art "Heritage of the Great Steppe" and "Kazakhstan - the heart of Eurasia" were organized. President of the Republic of Kazakhstan Nursultan Nazarbayev and Crown Prince of the Emirate of Abu Dhabi Sheikh Muhammad bin Zayed Al Nahyan were guests of the solemn concert in connection with the event(F-75H; I-1; Case-322).

Such benevolent endeavors to propagate the noble art and culture of Kazakhstani nation continued in Minsk, the Republic of Belarus, Ashgabat, Turkmenistan, and the cities of Riyadh and Saudi Arabia in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

Days of Culture of Kazakhstan were organized during the official visit of President of the Republic of Kazakhstan N.A. Nazarbayev to the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan. Leading masters of art of Kazakhstan presented to the public modern and classic works of art(F-54; I-1; Case-687). In addition, an exhibition of artists by Kazakhstan, an exhibition of jewelry by the famous jeweler B. Alibay, a book exhibition from the funds of the National Library of Kazakhstan, a photo exhibition reflecting the richness and peculiarity of the culture of the people of Kazakhstan were also organized at the A. Kastejev State Museum of Art. 1993-1994 According to the plan of cultural cooperation between Kazakhstan and China, an exhibition of Chinese applied art was organized at the A. Kastejev State Museum of Arts(F-75H; I-1; Case-1030), an exhibition of Kazakhstani works of art was held in Beijing.

The relations in the field of cultural partnership have been established since the arrival of the First Deputy Foreign Minister of India, Ruby Bhatia, to Kazakhstan. In January 1994, a literary evening of the Kazakh poet Amanzhol Shamkenov was organized in Delhi. From November 29 to December 5, 1994 a delegation of Indian writers and poets, led by the famous writer Ananta Murthy, visited Almaty. According to the Cultural Partnership Declaration, in 1997 protocols and interdepartmental plans for cultural exchanges were signed. 62 Kazakhstan travel agencies and firms have established cooperation with their counterparts in India. Sports associations are established between certain federations and clubs. Under the terms of the mutual agreements between the Field Hockey, Volleyball, Judo, Archery and Soccer Federations, in the conditions of India and Kazakhstan the athletes had joint exercises and friendly meetings with the above mentioned sports. An important milestone in strengthening cultural co-operation was the celebration of the 150th anniversary of Abay and Zhambyl in India, and the 125th anniversary of Mahatma Gandhi in Kazakhstan, and the translation of Abai's songs in Hindi. A delegation from India arrived in Kazakhstan to celebrate the anniversary of Abay and Zhambyl. In March 2000, Training Center has been opened at the Eurasian National University(F-75H; I-1; Case-3301).

A resident of Warsaw, Vladislav Sokolovsky, visited Polish cities and spoke about Kazakhstan in connection with the UN announcement of the Year of International Cultures for rapprochement. The yurt was sewed and an exhibition of Kazakh artists was organized. The paintings depict the life of a Kazakh village, dombra, kobyz, zhetygen(kazakh musical instrument) on a handmade carpet.

In addition, Abay's monument was erected in Moscow in April 2006 as part of the Action Plan for Abay in Russia and Pushkin Year in Kazakhstan. The opening ceremony was attended by the heads of states of Kazakhstan and Russia. Abay's monument will undoubtedly be a monument of eternal peace and unity of the two countries.

As it is known, at the beginning of the third millennium, independent and secular Kazakhstan was one of the first among the subjects of international law to take responsibility and in practice began to seriously and responsibly promote a global dialogue between the leaders of the world and traditional religions. 18 years ago, on September 23-24, 2003, the First Congress of Leaders of World and Traditional Religions was held in the capital of Kazakhstan Astana, which for the first time in the modern history of mankind, gathered at one table 17 delegations from Europe, Asia, the Middle East and America representing Christianity and Islam, Judaism and Buddhism, Hinduism, Taoism, and Shintoism.

The first Congress was held in a difficult atmosphere, during separate meetings with the Head of our state, religious leaders expressed complaints against each other, which clearly testified to the lack of a common view on the most acute problems of our time. Such contradictions were fueled by political problems between

states.

President N. Nazarbayev had to make a lot of efforts to bring them to a common denominator, nevertheless, the joint declaration was adopted, which marked the beginning of the subsequent dialogue between religions. Today, among the participants there is an understanding of the importance of continuing interreligious dialogue outside the context of political contradictions between states. In the 21st century, there is no alternative to dialogue in all spheres - political, economic, cultural, spiritual - and this is an immutable axiom that shows its relevance at the present time.

Today the history has set a difficult task for the upcoming Congress of Leaders of World and Traditional Religions: at the same time, to achieve continuation of interreligious dialogue, and to find ways to peacefully unite communities and states that are united by common interests (Congress Religions, 2015: 297).

In 2009 alone, 7 international treaties were sent through diplomatic channels for professional consideration:

- Draft Agreement on Cultural Cooperation between the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan and the Government of the Federal Republic of Brazil;

- Draft Memorandum of Understanding between the Ministry of Culture and Information of the Republic of Kazakhstan and the Ministry of Culture, Sports and Information of the Republic of Montenegro in the field of culture and information;

- Draft Memorandum of Understanding between the Ministry of Culture and Information of the Republic of Kazakhstan and the Ministry of Culture and Information of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in the field of culture and information;

- Draft agreement in the field of culture between the Ministry of Culture and Information of the Republic of Kazakhstan and the Ministry of Culture, Religion and National Heritage of Romania;

- Comprehensive Plan for the Development of Cultural and Humanitarian Cooperation between the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan and the Government of the Kyrgyz Republic for 2010-2011;

- Comprehensive Plan for the Development of Cultural and Humanitarian Cooperation between the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan and the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2010-2011;

- Undoubtedly, the draft Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan and the Government of the Republic of India on cooperation in the field of culture, art, media and sports will promote our culture.

In addition, during the year 2009 a memorandum of understanding and cooperation in the field of culture was signed with the 6 international treaties reached at the interstate level with the Sultanate of Oman, Kuwait, the Islamic Republic of Pakistan, the Turkish Republic, the Islamic Republic of Iran and the Czech Republic (Strategic plan, 2008: 27).

Since gaining sovereignty in Kazakhstan, various cultural events and business meetings have shown the interest of the world to independent Kazakhstan.

Conclusion

Today, Kazakhstan's high authority within the international organizations is achieved thanks to the positive policy and new approaches of the state. As of 2009, there are currently more than 70 agreements in the field of culture, media, and archives that fall under the jurisdiction of the Ministry.

Cultural relations in the modern world also have successful traditions of developing a dialogue on a multilateral basis. At the beginning of the twentieth century, intercultural relations sought to become an important source of international cooperation, a means of promoting peace based on high humanistic ideals.

These great movements in the world community on the basis of equal relations with civilized states, equal recognition of the inviolable population of the population with their indivisible culture, formation of innovative attitude of the state power to cultural life raise the cultural image of Kazakhstan in the world community. Once we have set up a sovereign country and set our sights on, instead of going into bigotry, instead moving on to real action, gaining world-renowned cultural supporters and strengthening cultural ties, we will always have a goal.

It is obvious that since the independence of Kazakhstan, the holding of various cultural events and business meetings has greatly enhanced the prestige of the country. During these events, the world community showed interest in an independent Kazakhstan. Maintaining friendly, predictable and mutually beneficial relations with foreign countries in bilateral and multilateral formats, the development of comprehensive cooperation with interstate associations and international organizations.

Reference

- Nazarbayev N.A. (2017). Era of Independence. Astana: Publishing house, p. 84.
- Ayagan B.G., Nurymbetova G.R., Abzhanov H.M. (2010). Institute of the presidency in Kazakhstan: history, lessons, experience. Almaty: Raritet, p.368.

- Tokaev K.K. (2000). Kazakhstan's foreign policy in the context of globalization. Almaty: SAK, p.584.
- Mukhamedov M.B. (2000).Kazakhstan in the world community. Almaty: Publishing center of the Higher attestation Commission, p.328.
- Mazhidenova D.M. (2011).Foreign cultural policy. //Public administration and activities. №1, pp. 59-61.
- Arystanbekova A. H. (2007). Globalization. Almaty: Drake-Press, p.238-258.
<https://www.academia.edu>
- Iskakova K. (2000). Multinationalism of Kazakhstan - the result of Soviet policy. //Kazakh History. No.5. September-October, pp. 55-59.
<https://www.osce.org/odihr/38008?download=true>
- Speech by Nursultan Nazarbayev(2007). at the Palace of Peace and accord at the expanded meeting of the Public Council for the implementation of the state program "Cultural heritage". <http://www.akorda.kz/>
- Statistical Yearbook of the Agency of the RK for Statistics. (2007). Astana: Daur, p. 56.
- Dauletov T. (2002).The Second world Congress of Kazakhs. Almaty: Press,p.65.
AP RK F-75H; I-1; Case-4113.
NA RK F-54; I-1; Case-591.
NA RK F-24; I-1; Case-126.
- SaudabayevK.B. (1999).The Kazakh-Turkish relations: the emergence, current state and prospects. Dissertation for the degree of doctor of political science. Almaty: KNTU, p.234-243.
- Kenzhebaev G.K. (2007).The development of international cooperation of the Republic of Kazakhstan in the field of higher education. //Kazakhstan Civilization, No.47. November 2, p. 22.
- Djumaliev A. (1995). The dissertation for the degree of candidate of historical sciences in the subject “Kazakh schools (history and development lessons) in 1975-1995”. Almaty: Rauan, p. 67.
NA RK F-27; I-1; Case-28.
- Masanov N. (1994). Culture of the Kazakh craft. Almaty: Atamura, p. 34.
NA RK F-27; I-1; Case-34.
NA RK F-27; I-1; Case-202.
- Negimov S. (2008). Independence and Nation // Language and Society, No. 3, December 1, p.7.
<http://cultural.kz/>
- 27th session of UNESCO. (2003). Paris, June 23.<http://whc.unesco.org/en/sessions/27com/documents/>
NA RK; F-54; I-1; Case- 208.
- Nurzhekeyev B. (2009). Sinful love: a story; translated by Chris Lovelace. Astana: Audarma, 120 p.
AP RK F-75N; I-1; Case-322.
NA RK; F-54; I-1; Case-687.
AP RK F-75N; I-1; Case-1030.
AP RK F-75N; I-1; Case-3301.
- Strategic plan of the Ministry of Culture and Information for 2009-2011, approved by the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan. (2008). dated December 23, Astana: Daur, No.1204, p. 27.
- Congress of Leaders of World and Traditional Religions. (2015). Executive editor R.Turlynova, Astana: Foliant, p. 297.

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